

Fisher's Historical Approach to the Religious Change in Igbo Land

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Abstract

This issue of religious change in Africa and Igbo land is a continuous debate which has been done by many scholars from their own point of view. However, this religious change or conversion is a continuous process. Fisher in this historical approach of religious change tries to show the process that is involved in conversion. From this, one sees that the situation of process of conversion in Igbo land is captured by historical approach explained by Fisher. The mass movement from African traditional religion to Christianity and Islam in the early times is captured, and the return of most Christian people to their traditional practices and religion is vividly explained by Fisher's historical approach through the process of conversion. This piece therefore submits that Fisher made a kind of prophecy or showed the way conversion may take place in future in the life of the Igbo people.

Introduction

Religious change in Africa or conversion has been viewed or studied by many scholars. Each of the findings, from all scholars portrayed religious change from different point of their views. Social scientists and historians have their own findings towards the phenomenon of conversion in Africa. This process of conversion is still ongoing in Africa but now taking different shapes or stages. According to Metuh (1987), any theory on the conversion or religious change in Africa must answer or investigate some crucial matters concerning the mass movement from African traditional religions to Islam and Christianity. The question now is, this massive movement, can it be called conversion? Again, what is the explanation of the high occurrence of independent and indigenous African church movements being seen today?

As we are going to see, the different explanations to religious change tend to highlight aspects of change or why there is continuity or discontinuity in one form of religion to another. Fisher (1973) in his historical analysis of conversion tends towards discontinuity and at the same time has element of continuity. It is only Fisher among all the religious theorists that captured the current situation of Igbo land towards conversion to Christianity. In the adhesion stage of

conversion Fisher explained that people stood with one foot on either side of the fence, adopting their new worship as useful supplements to the old. Again, the stages of religious conversion explain the current situation among the people found in Igbo land and Africa in general as regards to practice of their religion. The situation of relapsing into mixing or quarantine stage, having been in the reform stage for a long period of time and adopting new elements of another culture into theirs is a sign of continuous process of conversion.

The mass drift found today in Africa from traditional religion to Christianity and Islam, and back to traditional religion is an indication that most people are in the mixing stage. This can be captured or vividly seen in the syncretic practices seen in Igbo land and beyond, in all the things they do as regards to their religion and culture. Finally, this write up sets out to examine and highlight the gains and issues found in Fisher's historical analysis of religious change or conversion in Africa in general, particularly towards Igbo land.

Fisher's Historical Approach To Conversion

Humphery J. Fisher was a professor of history in the Oriental and African studies. He specialized in the religious history of pre-colonial Africa. So he stood on a good ground to examine the religious change in Africa and again to re-examine the intellectualist theory of Robin Horton on religious change in Africa. Fisher's historical approach to the study of religious conversion in Igbo land and African in general was as a reaction to Robin Horton's intellectual approach on African conversion. According to Fisher (1973):

The core of his argument is summarized thus... Horton's evidence is chiefly drawn from Christian African experience, though he seeks to generalize from it for both Islam and Christianity. My specific purpose here is to look more closely at the phenomena of Muslim conversion, and to see what light this may throw on Horton's argument... my other general purpose is to suggest that such Muslim/Christian comparisons may considerably enlarge our perspectives upon black Africa. (P. 27).

Fisher drew attention of all, that the fundamental thing here is neither the vigorous reconstruction of traditional African religion nor the effective transplanting of Islam and Christianity, rather the development of a higher religious awareness which transcends and subsumes current religious formulation. Pannenberg (cited by Fisher, 1973) tried to point out that

the struggle of religious traditions with each other points beyond the present to another form of religious unity which is trying to take shape in such struggles.

Pannenberg in this line of argument suggested that Christian missions, particularly during their nineteenth century expansion, drew together the different, more or less isolated religious traditions into a world history of religion. This will not be done by displacing these existing traditions, but helping to bring all religions into a relationship with one another. This differs greatly with Horton (1971) opinion that the microcosm filled with man's daily activity will collapse with the coming of macrocosm which is controlled by the Supreme God.

The issue of traditional religious unity has not been exploited in Africa. Fisher (1973) explained that there is in Africa a wealth of practical data which has perhaps not yet been sufficiently exploited by African theologians at large. What is seen today in Muslim or Christian in Africa is in reality the development of that which was inherit in the traditional African faiths. This explains why world religions (Islam and Christianity) will conform necessarily to some extent to the traditions or cultures of each people it found itself.

Fisher (1973) again criticized Horton's thought experiment, in which Horton tried to imagine the development of religion in Africa during the modern period, in the absence of Christianity and Islam. The obvious inference is that acceptance of Islam and Christianity is due to as much to development of the traditional cosmology in response to other features of the modern situation as it is to the activities of the missionaries. In response to the above, Fisher (1973) argues extensively that:

For two reasons, I find it difficult to accept. First, I do not see any sound historical reason for expecting that adherents of African traditional faiths will behave as Horton's thought experiment suggests- that they can only interpret changes in their society in a particular way, that they necessarily evolve a monotheistic moral code for the wider world, and so on. I find two specific difficulties. First, it is hard to distinguish just where, 'the pre-Islamic, pre-Christian phase, pre-modern social situation', or 'what might be called "standard" situation may be found'... even when approximate examples are found, they do not always behave in the way they should. (p. 29).

Fisher gave examples of places and societies like Northern and Central Ghana, Buganda, which have been exposed for long periods to the enlarging effects of international trade, and

Christian and Muslim presence, sufficient at least pump-priming for the growth of the cult of the Supreme Being, nothing tangible was seen. Again if there is to be a steady movement towards monotheism, Islam and Christianity have to be much more than catalysts.

Fisher suggested that even in purely pagan situations, movement of religious reforms, change or development have been in the air. Sudden outburst of enthusiasm leading to any one of reforms like destruction of fetishes, abandoning of traditional values, very often occur from time to time, not being simply the creation of the European colonial contact. Though Muslim and Christian contributions may not be neglected for such tendencies to be sustained or carried out. With Islam and Christianity being involved, Fisher (1973) agreed that literacy is necessary, otherwise much of the ground gained may be lost through backsliding later, for literacy facilitates eventual recovery. The second reason why Fisher rejected the thought experiment of Horton was that Horton neglected the evidence from Muslim black Africa, which of course formed the major burden of Fisher's historical approach.

Fisher pointed out that both Islam and Christianity have been deeply influenced by their African setting. This view made him popular as one of the scholars that did not destroy or derogate the image of African people and their religion as fetish, primitive, paganish or juju. Hence, he stressed much on the issue of comparative religions. He stressed the need to consider the general possibilities of Christian/Muslim comparison with African traditional religion in the African studies. Through this way, Fisher is casting African traditional religion among the major religions of the world. This also explains the ease with which Islam is accommodated in Africa. Fisher admitted that both faiths (Christianity and Muslim) have been influenced by Africa, so it is reasonable to assume that there must be certain common elements of influence in African traditional religions. Finally, Fisher (1973) confirmed that:

Such a comparative approach may substantially help our understanding, but also that the academic tools for beginning the task are now sufficient. It would still be difficult, I suppose, for an armchair theologian to work out a detailed comparison from published sources. But be a research worker, proposing to compare Islam and Christianity among- say Yao or Buganda, or in Lagos, or even in Cape Town, would have an abundance of background and supporting material to work through before ever he or she sets out for the field. (P. 31).

Fisher noticed or discovered a length of time uninterrupted which it will take a particular religion in a place to be where it is. This greatly enlarged time scale according to Fisher (1973) allows one to pick out more clearly an underlying Muslim/Christian pattern which is roughly characterized into three stages: quarantine, mixing and reform.

In the quarantine stage, according to Fisher (1973) the faith is represented by newcomers like traders, refugees or clerics employed in providing religious services such as prayer and divinations. In this first stage, orthodoxy is relatively secure because there are no real converts, and thus no one to bring into the Islam/Christian community heterodox beliefs and observances drawn from his or her non Muslim past. This idea of Fisher was aptly seen during the conversion of Igbo people where slaves and outcasts were mainly the people who were first to be converted. At this stage they know nothing about Christianity. Moreover, they were people, who because of their social disabilities had a grievance against traditional Igbo culture and society. Hence the Igbo people did not send their real and beloved children to church or school of the missionaries because they wanted to bring them up in the traditional life and culture. Rather they sent their slaves and poverty-stricken people. According to Nzekwu (1971) “the result was that they became the first people to learn to read and write, wear good dresses and make plenty of money...” (P. 87). This they did, according to Onwubiko (1991), not because of their likeness for the Christian religion, but in order not to lag behind since the new trend had proven that the new culture had something in it that must be acquired.

Just like Fisher (1973) noted, the stage of quarantine is always filled up with new comers as we have seen above. The stage of quarantine is not maintained indefinitely because the new local people as they are being converted in increasing numbers, the stage of mixing ensues. In this stage of mixing, people newly converted combine the profession of their religions with new coming one, which may be Islam or Christianity. Finally, after a lapse of years and centuries, the candle of reform which is the third stage comes in. this is kept alight by the written word, and mostly by the devotion of some converts and priests who succeeded in maintaining the element of quarantine against the mixing and restores the orthodoxy of quarantine stage.

This process we see above does not start at the same time everywhere, nor advance everywhere at the same pace, so that examples of these three stages may be found in almost any period and anywhere. Hence there is no uniformity in the progress of conversion. Fisher (1973) however noted that the reform may prove burdensome to maintain and there will be tendency to

slip back into mixing, the three cycles may continue to repeat itself. Fisher tried to fit the three fold sequence of quarantine, mixing and reform into conversion. In quarantine stage, there is no large-scale conversion. The first converts had to pass into the separate world of their new faith. The first Christians were outsiders: slaves in America, captives in Sierra-Leone, odd men outprised from their former status and society. This view was expressed by Afigbo (1981) in the early stages of Christianity in Igbo land when he said that:

The first generation of Igbo Christians thus had limited attachment to their traditional culture, and in fact, from the beginning tended to pitch themselves against it. As a result, while time and death thinned down the defenders of the old order, the ranks of the Christians were progressively being augmented. This is a point not always been stressed in discussions on the spread of Christianity in Igbo land. (p. 340).

Achebe (1958) captured also the picture of first Christians thus:

These outcast, or osu, seeing that the new religion welcomed twins and such abominations, thought that it was possible that they would also be received. And so one Sunday two of them went into the church. There was an immediate stir; but so great was the work the new religion had done among the converts that they did not immediately leave the church when the outcasts came in. (p. 125).

Conversion in the first stage (quarantine) in a traditional society often is a difficult step and it arouses scorn among the people with dominant faith.

When the quarantine barriers are over, the people begin to voluntarily convert to the new religion (mixing) which is now the second stage. There are many problems being encountered here by new converts. The Muslims receive the traditional religion with ease unlike Christianity. According to Fisher (1973), mixing in Christianity involves often lengthy catechuminate, perhaps a literacy requirement, probationary periods, while for Islam the profession of faith is usually sufficient as a beginning.

Nock (cited by Fisher, 1973) finds a middle position in which religion develops step by step with political advance and cultural exchange. Nock identifies these factors like conquest, trade, slavery, military services, inter-marriage on their own does not lead individuals making a decisive switch of allegiance. Instead, people stood with one foot on either side of the fence, adopting the new worships as useful supplements. This Nock calls adhesion which he contrasted

with conversion, being deliberately turning from indifference or from an earlier form of piety to another, a turning which implies a consciousness that a great change is involved, that the old was wrong and the new is right. It is in Nock's adhesion that one can explain the sort of loyalty many African traditional religion found itself with other religions of the world.

After a long period of mixing, various factors were seen to be of great importance in preserving the orthodoxy learnt from any of the two world religions. Literacy or education was particularly important, not only as a lifetime of orthodoxy during mixing periods, but as a chief weapon of reformers. This is vividly seen in the case of conversion in Igbo land. According to Afigbo (1981):

The success of the Christian missions in Igbo land, like in many other parts of Africa was brought about not so much by preaching "Christ crucified" as through the parade of the advantages of literacy over illiteracy, that is through the school. In the earlier phase of Christian evangelism in Igbo land, the missionaries advanced by direct preaching to the elders, appeal through social services like medical clinics and orphanages and the establishment of Christian villages. Practical experiences and hard thinking soon shared that these methods could not work the magic of converting the Igbo to Christianity in large numbers. The decision of the missionaries to use the school as their instrument of proselytization became a turning point in the history of Christianity in Igbo land. Through schools, the missions exploited to some advantage the burning desire of the Igbo to become as expert as the British in the manipulation of their physical world. In effect the Igbo were not converted to Christianity; they were ensnared to Christianity by the school. (p. 340).

Again, Mead (cited by Fisher, 1973) emphasized the importance of education as weapon of conversion when she said that:

Primitive education was a process by which continuity was maintained between parents and children... modern education includes a heavy emphasis upon the function of education to create discontinuities- to turn the child... of the illiterate into the literate. (p. 34).

Fisher (1973) in his analysis pointed out that the Quram school (muslim) used primitive education while the mission school (Christianity) used modern education in the teaching of their new converts or those in quarantine. With the introduction of literacy or education in a formerly non literate society, it freezes most of the traditional beliefs and exposes them to social change.

Though in practical effect, illiteracy conserves the status quo in belief and behavior (conservative), but literacy can introduce radical changes (revolution).

Fisher (1973) was of the position that literacy serves also as a time-bomb of reform, sometimes with a fuse smouldering if need be over centuries, but with the powder of the main charge kept dry. With time the explosion may take place in form of conversion. This may lead to two religious development or conversion. First may be exchanging one faith (or none) for another, and secondly exchanging indifference and dilution for fervency within the same faith. The second meaning or type of conversion is more or clearer in western tradition. Nock (cited by Fisher, 1973) summed it up thus:

This type of experience is very well known. We must not, however, expect to find exact analogies for it beyond the range of countries with long-standing Christian tradition. For in them even when the fact of conversion appears wholly sudden and not led up to by a gradual process of gaining conviction, even when the convert may in all good faith profess that the beliefs which have won his sudden assent are new to him, there is a background of concepts to which a stimulus can give life... such conversions is in its essence a turning away from a sense of present wrongness at least as much as a turning towards a positive ideals. (p. 36-37).

Fisher accuses Horton of concentrating only on the first stage of conversion that is exchanging one faith (or none) for another. This means that the essential underlying movement of religious growth, through the first conversion towards the second is lost. Again, each of these kinds of religious change has their own factors or causes of change.

Finally, according to Metuh (1987):

It must be said that Fisher is guilty of a similar omission. He was so taken up with the second type of conversion that he forgot the first step of conversion. How did the local people come to adopt Islam in the first place? Fisher does not say. And this is in fact what Horton's article tries to explain. So Fisher's arguments do not challenge Horton's main thesis. (p. 17).

Ifeka-moller (1974) also accused Fisher of not accounting for cases and causes of difficult conversion nor did he even recognize the cases of difficult conversions. Fisher (1973) only mentioned the ease with which the Islam was accepted in black Africa. Though Fisher's description of conversion is quite different from Ifeka-moller's explanation of conversion, which

is understood as either a change of affiliation from cult (traditional religion) to church, or from orthodox Christianity to spiritualist church.

Again, it has to be noted that Fisher based his research mostly on Islam and only compared it with Christianity in relation to traditional religion. Hence, most of the information or data he has was about Islam and not Christianity. In effect his explanation on religious change in black Africa may not be complete and sound, for both religions played its part simultaneously on African soil. Fisher (1973) blamed Horton on the above mistake and fall in it again when he said that “Horton’s evidence is chiefly drawn from Christian- African experience, though he seeks to generalize from it for both Islam and Christianity” (p. 27).

However, there are many merits of Fisher’s historical approach analysis to religious change in Africa, which will be seen in the effects of religious change in Igbo land. But one must not fail to see how Fisher’s analysis underscored the importance of factors internal to the religion to which conversion is made from traditional religion to world religions.

Issues from Fisher’s Historical Approach to the Religious Change in Igbo Land.

Religious change in Igbo land today visibly found itself in the state of adhesion. A situation according to Fisher (1973), where people stood with one foot on either sides of the fence, thereby adopting the new elements as useful supplements of worship. It is well known that Igbo people or African people are combining either of the two world religions with their own traditional religion especially in solving their problems and in worship. This is purely adhesion rather than conversion. This is why in times of sickness, serious misfortune, deaths, desire for progress, the Igbo man always consults the traditional God to know what to do or how to extricate himself or his household from problem. Hence divination can never stop in Igbo traditional religious practices.

This is always the case with the Igbo man believes that there are certain things which the new religions cannot take care of. For example, the widely known oath taking between Chris Ngige and Chris Uba at *Okija* shrine during the Anambra state governorship election. According to Alozieuwa (2009):

The idea of taking Ngige to the shrine actually emanated from Chuma, whose country home is just some stone throw to *Okija* town where the *Ogwugwu Akpu* goddess resided, said Odunze. According to him, he (Odunze), had just come in from Umunya

when Ngige informed him that Eselu had said that Chuma asked him that they took him (Ngige) to *Okija* shrine, and that Eselu had already consented to it. (p. 112).

From the above situation, whether the above event or scenario took place or not, one notices the importance and role of Igbo traditional religion among the people which cannot be offered by other world religions. For they believe strongly in the efficacy of traditional God whom they are accustomed with, before the arrival of Christian religion. Hence the persistence of Igbo traditional religion is not in doubt and this confirms Fisher's adhesion in terms of religious change, for this cannot be called conversion.

In a bid to solve their problems or crisis, the Igbo or African people went further from adhesion to establish or found African Independent churches (A.I.C). These churches take care of the problems relating to Igbo man or African people with regard to their culture, and it effectively combines one of the world religions with African traditional practices, and this ensures independence of churches owned by African people. Ejizu (1985) listed some of these churches, like Chief K. O. K Onyioha's Godianism, which claims to be the modern version of Igbo traditional religion. The Odozi-obodo prayer healing home of *nwanyi* Ufuma, which has Christian outlook but draws inspiration from Igbo traditional religion. The *Ogboni* fraternity and *Eruosa* national church among the Yoruba and Edo people of Nigeria respectively. The African Independent *Aladura* churches, including the *Kimbangu* church of Congo, and the Cherubim and Seraphim groups, all are in a bid to keep alive aspects of the indigenous religious culture of the African people.

Ndiokwere (2019) affirms the above by asserting that:

It was not only the Europeans who had the divine mandate to go and make disciples of all nations... (Mt. 23:19). Discipleship was the universal vocation of every Christian, but Africans are not stopping at founding churches and religious movements. In the near-absurd extension of their idea of discipleship and mission, African prophets and self-proclaimed religious leaders found and run churches of their grass-root tastes. (p. 9-10).

This confirms the Fisher's (1973) assumptions that each religion bears the culture of a place and so conversion is a difficult process and it does involve replacing, combining or exchanging of values or culture willingly. Adhesion cannot totally be the reason for the establishment of thousands of churches in Africa. For many scholars still point out the aftermath of Berlin

conference and the partitioning of Africa by the world powers. Hence, Christian missionary organizations followed the flags of their respective nations to the shores of African nations. The acrimony created by such divisions has continued or activated the proliferation of churches in Africa, but the issue of adhesion remained at the centre of this proliferation. According to Smith (cited by Agazue, 2015):

The number of prosperity churches is huge, with entrepreneurial pastors starting new churches seemingly every day. Pentecostalism has become the fastest growing industry in Nigeria, and the second most popular export (after crude oil). Churches in Nigeria... now out-number schools, clinics and banks all put together. (P.1-2).

From the above, one can conclude that Fisher (1973) through his historical approach to religious change in Africa made a kind of prophecy or prepared the ground or terrain through which religion in Africa will pass or its outcome with its contact with world religions.

The stages in religious change or process of conversion as enumerated by Fisher include quarantine, mixing and reform. These stages can be equated with what the modern theologians of today call inculturation, adaptation, faith integration, translation, indigenization, contextualization, acculturation and so on. Inculturation and other terms used above are relatively new in theology. Muonwe (2014) asserts that these plethora of terms had been employed over the years in an attempt to fashion out the best model or approach to be adopted in relating Christian faith and traditional religion. Though Muonwe still argues that “The encounter between faith and culture that happens in the process of inculturation is very dynamic and so deep to be visualized as mere mixture, intermingling; much less adaptation or assimilation.” (p. 96).

Though within the context of Fisher’s historical approach, he did not set out to interpret traditional religion with Christianity or Islamic religion but only explaining the processes involved in religious change. So Fisher (1973) should be applauded for his attempt in helping to explain the process of conversion which is the task of African theologians, especially as it regards to traditional religion to Christian religion.

Fisher argued that in the process of conversion with its three stages involved, that a convert in the mixing stage can relapse into quarantine, or reformed Christian can again go back to mixing and then quarantine stage. The cycle may go in the opposite direction which may take years before reaching reform stage or go back permanently to quarantine stage. In the process of conversion in Igbo land today, many young people and aged ones including the elites are going

back to their original or traditional faith. Thus the growth or revival in the traditional religion is being noticed in most of the Igbo land. This confirms the assumption or theory of Fisher above. Obiefuna (1985) succinctly confirmed the above by saying that:

Christianity has made an impact among our people. There is no gainsaying it. Many also avail themselves of the sacraments. But times without number the remark reaches us that our Christians are worshipping 'idols', false gods. They swear on idols... Catechist seminarians on apostolic work in the towns and villages are stunned at the degree of idol worship and superstitious practices that still exist among a people that are mostly baptized Catholics. (p. 5-6).

This is purely one of the syncretic practices found among Igbo people. This affirms that the traditional beliefs and practices are still very much on stage in contemporary Igbo society despite being schooled in Christian religion for centuries. Again Leith-Ross (cited by Ejizu, 1985), made her observation that an Igbo man attends communion, at the same time he ties up to his waist traditional medicine for protection. This accounts why divination will continue in Igbo land. This according to Metuh (1985) is what Ezeanya referred to as the endurance of conviction. This is against the philosophy of total rout enunciated by Achebe (1958) and Anyandele (1973).

From Fisher's historical approach to religious change, the stage of religious change is very much in vogue in Igbo land especially as it relates to relapsing to quarantine and mixing stages. This gives serious concern to the spiritual leaders of the Christian fold. Having seen some issues with regards to historical approach of Fisher, one can agree that it has helped to explain the nature of religious life of the Igbo people, and this will help to understand the persistent nature of the culture and values of Igbo people.

Conclusion

Just as the tide of religious change in Africa and Igbo land took a phenomenal dimension of increase in earlier years towards Christianity, also phenomenal decrease in the same Christian religion took place to enrich or increase the return to African traditional religion. This in a bit portrays the historical approach of Fisher on religious change in Igbo land and Africa in general. Though many factors, like western education and urbanization, according to Metuh (1985) had the eroding effects, on the grips of traditional beliefs. Recently, there is again resurgence of

interest in the traditional religion and culture among the elites of the Igbo people. This is captured aptly in the study of Fisher's theory on religious change.

Fisher in a way predicted revivalism which traditional religion and Christianity in Igbo land and Africa in general are undergoing. The mixing stage in the process of conversion showed such. Equally, Metuh (1985) captured such revivalism within Christianity in Igbo land and Africa as inspired by the need to tune missionary Christianity packaged in European cultural forms to the needs of African peoples. And this gave birth to the separatist church movements as noted earlier. These African churches are independent and indigenous in the sense that they not only had African founders, but their independence has allowed them to present Christianity in an African way and culture which is being preached to Africans.

Finally, Fisher's historical analysis of conversion within Africa and Igbo land highlights the major fact that conversion itself is a continuous process which is noticed very well in Igbo land today. Though, it is characterized by a number of tensions which involve adaptations of elements of traditional beliefs and adoption of new beliefs.

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